

THE ETYMOLOGY OF CONCEPT “HOLIDAY” IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LINGUISTICS

N.Gofurova

Fergana State University, p.f.f.d.,

Bakhromova Odina Abdurakhimovna

FSU, Linguistics: English language, Master’s Degree student

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the comparative analysis of the lexical units that verbalize the concept of “holiday” in English and Uzbek, which explores the similarities and differences of lexical units in both languages, reveals the factors that require them.

Key words and phrases: holiday, etymology, individuality, communication, concept, linguistics, ceremony, cognitive linguistics.

The research studies in the field of cognitive linguistics can illustrate the direction of cognitive linguistics is one of the most controversial areas of linguistics, which studies mental processes and their expression in the everyday life of people. Each person has his/her own communicative purpose and pragmatic features of his language, which reflect the picture of the world that arises from the process of synthesizing everything around him in his mind. This section of our research work is mainly devoted to the analysis of the concept, one of the research aspects of cognitive linguistics.

Cognitive linguistics encompasses a number of broadly compatible theoretical approaches to the meaning and structure of language, which share a common foundation: language is an integral part of communication, reflecting the interaction of cultural, psychological, and communicative factors. The main theory of cognitive linguistics is that linguistic cognition is an integral phenomenon of general human cognition, and therefore, we can observe the reflection in language of the cognitive functions and structures observed by psychologists, neurobiologists, and similar professionals. According to the theories of cognitive linguistics, meaning is a central issue, and along with the meaning of words, there is also the meaning of sentences; in other words, any linguistic expression, regardless of its small or large size, has its own meaning and content. The term “concept” is widely used in various scientific fields. The words “concept” and “notion” are often used synonymously, however, these two words differ in context. For example, in the works of the linguist E. S. Kubryakova, the term “concept” includes several areas of research and defines

the specific boundaries of the theory, and explains their main categories. Etymologically, this term was mentioned by the Russian linguist Askoldov in 1928. The linguist said that a concept is “a unit that reflects the process of thinking about one type or another of concepts” (1). (2)

If we give examples of historical manuscripts and works about the origin of the term “bayram” in the field of Uzbek linguistics, this concept is mainly found in “Avesto”, Abulkasim Firdawsi’s “Shokhnoma”, Tabari’s “Tarihi Tabari”, Abu Rayhan Beruni’s “Relics of the Ancient Peoples”, “Tafhim”, “Konuni Mas’udi”, Mas’udi’s “Muruj az-Zahab”, Omar Khayyam’s “Navruznom”, Mukhammad Husayn Burhan’s “Persnama”, Hafiz Abru’s “Zubdat-at-tavorikh”, Alisher Navoi’s “Saddi Iskandari”, “Khazoyin ul-Maoni”.

In Uzbek linguistics, words such as *shodiyona* and *tantana* are used as the main synonyms for the concept of “*Bayram*”. The origin of this concept goes back to the Persian word *pabrām* - *bayram*. Also, holidays can be expressed in two ways, that is, officially declared holidays (Independence Day, Women's Day) and traditional holidays (Flower Day, Tulip Day, Threshing Day, Melon Day). So, a holiday is mainly understood as celebrating an important event or date in life (in high spirits and with joy). The expression of the concept of a holiday also depends on the culture of nations. In the Uzbek nation, on the eve of a holiday, people congratulate each other; express good wishes to each other, and wish success, luck, and happiness in their work. They give each other various gifts.

The “O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati” provides the following definitions of the concept of “holiday”:

1. Bayram – muhim, tarihiy voqea, hodisa sharafiga shodlik, rasmiy tantana o‘tkazish uchun belgilangan muborak kun: *Bayram oldi musobaqa*. (Holiday - a blessed day designated for joy and official celebration in honor of an important, historical event, event: a pre-holiday competition.)
2. Biror munosabat bilan quvonch, shodlik, tantana va o‘yin-kulgi bilan kutib olish, nishonlash odat bo‘lib qolgan kun: *Yangi yil bayrami*. *Archa bayrami*. *Navro‘z bayramidan keyin Isfandiyorxon qazuvga chiqishga farmon berdi*. (J.Sharipov. Xorazm). (A day when it is customary to welcome and celebrate with joy, happiness, celebration and fun: New Year’s holiday. Spruce holiday. After the Navruz holiday, Isfandiyorxon ordered to go on an excavation. (J. Sharipov. Khorezm)
3. Muhim, quvonchli hodisa yuz bergan, katta muvaffaqiyat qo‘lga kiritilgan va shu sababli shodlik bilan o‘tkaziladigan kun: *Oilaviy bayram*. *Qishloq tarixida birinchi qurilgan ko‘rkam maktabning katta bayramga aylangan tantanasi ishda*

g'ayrat ko'rsatganlarga mukofotlar ulashish bilan tugadi. (P.Tursun, O'qituvchi).
(A day when an important, joyful event occurred, a great success was achieved and therefore celebrated with joy: Family holiday. The grand opening of the first beautiful school built in the history of the village, which turned into a big holiday, ended with the distribution of awards to those who showed diligence in work. (P. Tursun, Teacher) (3)

Furthermore, in the "O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati" we can see other forms of the concept "bayram": *bayrambozlik, bayramlashmok, bayramlik.*

If we turn to the etymology of the concept of "bayram", the "O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati" defines the term "bayram" as "*Tantana, shodlik bilan o'tkaziladigan kun, muborak kun*": The day we heard that my daughter had become a university student was a holiday in our family. This noun was originally formed by adding the suffix *-ir (r)* to the *-bay* form of the verb *-baz*, which means *-yayil, -yayra* in the ancient Turkic language, and the suffix *-m*, which expresses the meaning of strengthening; later the narrow vowel in the second syllable was not pronounced; In Uzbek, the vowels *-a* have changed their meaning: *-baz-bay+ir=bayir+a+m=bayram*, which was later changed to the form *-bayram*. Mahmud Koshgari also noted that the original meaning of this word was pronounced as *-bazram*, and that the Oghuz changed the *-z* consonant to *-y* consonant and pronounced it as *-bayram*. (4)

It should be noted that the word "Holiday", which expresses the concept of holiday in English, is a homonym and expresses the meanings of holiday and holiday:

We are planning to holiday in Europe next summer. - We are planning to holiday in Europe next summer. In this example, we can see that the word "holiday" is used in the meaning of vacation.

The store is decorated with holiday lights and ornaments.- The store is decorated with holiday lights and ornaments. The given example can represent the meaning of a holiday.

Moreover, in English, the words *furlough, leave, vacation* are used as synonyms for the concept of "holiday".

To summarize, in English and Uzbek linguistics, the concepts representing the word "holiday" simultaneously represent different meanings, and we can see that the origins of these words and the forms of the word have changed as people and their cultural consciousness have developed.

List of used literature:

1. Askoldov S.A. / Concept and word, Russian literature. From the theory of literature to the structure of the text.// Anthology-M:Academia. 1997.-C.267-280
2. Gulmira Akhmadaliyeva / Classification of paremias associated with the concept of “fear” through cognitive layers // Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal, 2024, 32-38 p
3. Z.M.Ma’rufov / Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language // Moscow, 1981, 73-p
4. Sh.Rahmatullayev / Etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language // Tashkent, 2000, 37-p

